

**BENIGN, BACKGROUND
AND PRECANCER DISEASES OF THE NECK
UTERUS**

Master degree 2nd course of the National university of Uzbekistan

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Annotation. *Cervical cancer is one of those rare cancers that can be prevented because most cases, they appear against the background of long-term precancerous diseases. The problem of background and precancerous diseases of the cervix of the uterus is of great biomedical and socio-economic importance, since the treatment of patients with precancerous processes requires significantly less material costs than the treatment of cancer patients, ensures complete rehabilitation of patients and improves quality and duration of their life.*

Fundamentally new methods are not required for early detection of cervical cancer. Pathology can be diagnosed using generally accepted clinical, endoscopic and morphological methods in various combinations.

Key words: *cervix, dysplasia, cancer .*

The incidence of cancer of the organs of the reproductive system is an indicator of society's concern for the health and life of women.

Despite the availability of screening, cervical cancer (CC) in Belarus ranks third among malignant tumors of the reproductive system in women, behind breast cancer and uterine cancer. In 2014, 924 cases of cervical cancer were detected.

Certain types of cancer, such as cervical cancer and others, are considered potentially preventable, since in most cases they develop against the background of long-term precancerous processes.

Back in 1996 , WHO stated that cervical cancer is a potentially preventable

disease. Nearly 80% of cervical cancer cases occur in low-income countries. CC does not appear at lightning speed: according to WHO, the transition of dysplasia lasts an average of 3-8 years. Another 10-15 years pass before the development of micro-invasive cancer. It has been established that more than 80% of lesions of the cervix are due to background diseases and 20% are precancerous. Women of reproductive age are a special risk group. Despite significant advances in the study and treatment of pathological conditions of the cervix, this problem continues to attract the attention of scientists and practitioners, since diseases of the cervix lead to impaired reproductive function, miscarriage and impaired labor activity.

It is possible to recognize the disease in time using generally accepted clinical, endoscopic and morphological methods in various combinations.

However, most researchers point to the low oncological alertness of doctors.

Diagnosis and treatment of benign diseases of the cervix is difficult due to the lack of a unified approach to their classification, clinical assessment, and, consequently, treatment tactics. This encourages practitioners to unjustified radicalism or, conversely, long-term conservative management of patients [8, 10, 13, 18, 19, 27, 30]. Structural and functional features of the cervix The cervix as a target organ, together with the body of the uterus, is a single functional formation. Length in the norm is 38.3–42.8 mm, diameter 20–30 mm, wall thickness 10 mm.

In the embryonic period, the cervix is formed by the fusion of the Mullerian canals at 12–16 weeks of embryogenesis, the isthmus (isthmus), together with the cervix, is a continuation of the body of the uterus.

At the site of attachment of the vaginal vaults, the cervix is divided into two parts: supravaginal and vaginal. The cervical canal is spindle-shaped. Its length from the external pharynx to the isthmus is not more than 40 mm.

At different age periods of a woman's life, the cervix has its own clinical

and morphological features that determine the options for topographic and anatomical relationships in it.

The vaginal part of the cervix, the exocervix, is covered with stratified squamous epithelium (SSE) and consists of approximately 15–20 cell layers. The main function of the exocervix is protective, due to its multilayer nature, as well as the presence of keratin and glycogen in the cells. Granules glycogen in the upper layers of the MPE create an immunological barrier, providing local immunity. Epithelium of exocervix and vagina has a similar structure and undergoes cyclical changes under the influence of hormones. MPE is represented by 4 types of cells: basal, parabasal, intermediate and superficial. The wall of the cervix consists of muscle and connective tissue, in which nerves and blood vessels (stroma) are located. The muscle tissue of the cervix provides a locking function outside of ovulation and during pregnancy. In childbirth, it forms the lower uterine segment. Endocervix - mucous membrane cervical canal, is represented by a single-row high cylindrical epithelium with a basally located nucleus. The main function of the cylindrical epithelium is secretory. The quantity and quality of mucus depends on the hormonal level.

Morphologically, three types of epithelium are distinguished on the cervix:

1. High cylindrical or prismatic, it is also endocervical.
2. True (original) stratified squamous (squamous) epithelium (MPE, MSE).
3. Metaplastic flat (transitional) epithelium.

Outer throat area of the junction of two epithelium: stratified squamous and cylindrical. The border of various types of epithelium in the cervix is called a junction or connection, its location changes at different age periods of a woman's life. In most cases, the transition boundary (junction) between the MPE and the columnar epithelium coincides with the area of the external os. With the growth and development of the body, the influence of hormonal balance, the transition zone shifts to the area of the external os, and ectopia disappears, but in 30% of

cases ectopia can also occur in reproductive age.

During pregnancy, changes normally occur in all structures that make up the cervix as a whole, as a result of which the prismatic junction normally moves to the ectocervix, with the formation of physiological ectopia. In menopause against the background of age-related involutive processes in the reproductive system, there is a shift of the transition zone to the lower part of the endocervix. A feature of this period is the appearance of atrophic and dystrophic changes in the epithelium and stroma of the cervix. Age-related features of the pathological processes of the cervix due to changes in the location of the junction of the epithelium:

- 1) girls tend to spread the inflammatory process (vulvo-vaginitis);
- 2) in women of reproductive age - a tendency to inflammatory and proliferative changes, traumatic damage. Dysplasia and cancer are more often localized on the ectocervix;
- 3) in postmenopausal women, atrophic-dystrophic changes, and malignancy of the epithelium is often found in the cervical canal.

There are more than 10 classifications of pathological processes of the cervix. Data on histophysiology and pathology of the cervix are reflected in modern classifications of diseases of the female genital organs,

International Nomenclature of Diseases (MNB, Volume VIII), International Classification of Diseases (ICD) 10th revision (1992) and in the Histological Classification of Tumors (GKO) of the female reproductive system (2nd edition, 1994) [6, 10, 13, 17 –19, 27–32]. Among practitioners in our country, the classification of pathological processes of the cervix, proposed by I.A. Yakovleva and B.G. Kukute in 1977 [18, 19]. The most acceptable classification in practical health care is the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision of the WHO (1995). N72.0 - Inflammatory disease of the cervix: cervicitis, endocervicitis, exocervicitis with or without erosion or ectropion. N74.0 -

Inflammatory diseases of the female pelvic organs in diseases classified elsewhere
Tuberculous infection of the cervix. N80.8 Endromyosis other (involves cervix)
N84.1 - Polyp of the cervix. N86 - Erosion and ectropion of the cervix.

Decubital (trophic) ulcer of the cervix. Eversion of the cervix. Excluded with cervicitis. N87 - Dysplasia of the cervix.

Cervical carcinoma excluded. N87.0 Mild cervical dysplasia Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia I degree.

N87.1 Moderate cervical dysplasia Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia II degree.

N87.2 Severe cervical dysplasia, not elsewhere classified.

N87.9 Cervical dysplasia, unspecified N88 - Other non-inflammatory diseases of the cervix. Inflammatory diseases of the cervix and cervical polyp were excluded.

N88.0 Leukoplakia of the cervix. N88.1 - Old rupture of the cervix. Excluded

current obstetric trauma. N88.2 - Stricture and stenosis of the cervix Excluded as a complication of childbirth. N88.3 Cervical insufficiency Examination and care for

isthmocervical insufficiency outside of pregnancy. N88.4.

Hypertrophic elongation of the cervix. N88.8 - Other specified non-inflammatory diseases of the cervix Clinical forms of pathological processes of the cervix Benign background diseases are conditions in which epithelial normoplasia is preserved, that is, proper division, differentiation, maturation, aging and rejection of epithelial cells occur. Benign background diseases include: ectopia of the prismatic epithelium, benign transformation zone, exo- and endocervicitis, true

erosion, polyps, ectropion, endometriosis, atrophic epithelium, leukoplakia without atypia, granulation tissue, cervical hypertrophy, and old cervical rupture. Erosion of the cervix is characterized by the absence of a stratified squamous epithelium in a certain area of the vaginal part of the cervix with exposure of the connective stroma.

Erosions of a specific etiology (syphilitic and tuberculous) are extremely

rare, mainly in young women. Trophic, traumatic erosions are detected mainly in postmenopausal women. Pseudo-erosion (ectopia) is the replacement of the squamous epithelium by a cylindrical epithelium emanating from the cervical canal, which is more often observed in women with cervical ruptures during childbirth and due to its deformation during scarring. In such cases, the inverted mucous membrane of the cervical canal extends beyond the external pharynx, forming a pseudo-erosion. Cervicitis (exo, endocervicitis) is an inflammatory process of the mucous membranes of the cervix. There are focal and diffuse cervicitis. Downstream - acute and chronic. Etiology - specific and non-specific. Polyp - connective tissue outgrowths with an epithelial cover. According to the structure, glandular and epidermal polyps are distinguished. Leukoplakia is keratinization of the mucosa, which looks like a whitish plaque with a hard-to-remove plaque. Ectropion is an eversion of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal. Endometriosis of the cervix transformation of the endometrium on the wound surface of the cervix after manipulations on cervix. Atrophic epithelium is usually the result of estrogen deficiency. More common in postmenopausal women. At the same time, the ectocervix epithelium is thin, pale, easily injured, subepithelial vessels are strongly translucent.

A benign transformation zone is the process of overlapping (epithelization) of columnar epithelium by stratified squamous epithelium. Cervical dysplasia is a precancerous disease that occurs in the presence of background processes or against its visually unchanged background. Dysplasia is a purely morphological concept, determined by microscopic examination. Cells with dysplasia are characterized by a change in the size and shape of their nucleus, the appearance of many dividing cells in them. There are the following forms of dysplasia: mild; moderate and severe. Methods for diagnosing diseases of the cervix

white) and does not reflect the essence of the pathological process. Behind the same symptom, various diseases can be hidden (with contact bleeding - from

colpitis to cancer). Complaints specific to individual diseases are practically absent. The main task of the anamnesis is to determine the presence of predisposing factors to the development of pathology: endocrine disorders, the outcome of childbirth, surgical interventions (diathermocoagulation, cryotherapy and laser destruction), long-term, recurrent "erosions", as well as the presence of oncological pathology in close relatives. Examination of the cervix with the help of mirrors makes it possible to conditionally divide women into two groups: 1 – practically healthy and 2 - with a modified cervix, requiring additional examination. However, examination of the cervix with the naked eye does not allow one to reliably judge the absence of pathology. The Schilleras test with 3% Lugol's solution is based on the tropism of the multilayer epithelium cell to iodine.

The test is considered negative if iodine-negative areas are found on the cervix, positive - with a uniform dark brown staining of a healthy MPE. The intensity of staining depends on the content of glycogen in the cells, which is due to the estrogen saturation of the woman's body. Colposcopic examination. Colposcopy - examination of the surface of the vaginal part of the cervix using a colposcope at a standard magnification (10-15x). The method is based on the detection of different relief of the mucous membrane and the type of vessels in normal and pathologically altered epithelium of the vaginal part of the cervix. The goal is to identify lesions of the ectocervix epithelium, determine their nature and localization; differential diagnosis of benign changes in the ectocervix, vagina and vulva; substantiation of the expediency of cervical biopsy, determination of the site and method of taking material for histological examination; also the choice of treatment pathology. Methods of colposcopic examination Simple (survey) colposcopy is an indicative method, without the use of medications. The shape and size of the cervix, the state of its surface, the presence and nature of ruptures, the border of the squamous and cylindrical epithelium are determined. The color

and relief of the mucous membrane of the ectocervix, the features of the vascular pattern and the nature of the discharge are assessed.

Extended colposcopy - examination of the catcervix using epithelial and vascular tests, in which the reaction of tissues in response to treatment with medicinal formulations (3% acetic acid solution and Lugol's solution) is observed. histological examination of the epithelium of the cervix using various dyes.

Colposcopy through color filters is used for a more detailed study of the epithelium and vascular pattern. To identify the features of the vascular system, a green filter is used, which completely absorbs long-wave infrared radiation.

Cervicoscopy - examination of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal using a cervicoscope or hysteroscope, which determines the nature of the folding of the mucosa, the presence of polyps, ulcerations, transformation zones and areas of atypical epithelium. Morphological research methods The cytological method is based on the study and evaluation of cellular material in order to identify the morphological features of cells that characterize specific pathological processes.

The first attempts to clarify the pathology of the cervix using the cytological method date back to the 1920s. In 1949, GN Papanicolaou coined the term "cervical dysplasia" and created a classification of cervical smears (Pap-smear-test) - the most used so far.

Methods for obtaining cell material: - punctate - the study of punctate;
- exfoliative - study of secretion and excretion; - excochleation - the study of scrapings taken with tampons, sharp objects from the lesions. – aspiration cytology – examination of aspirates.

Material for cytological examination:

- scraping from the endocervix, ectocervix and the junction zone of the MPE and CE;
- scraping or aspirate from the affected area;
- punctate neoplasms of the vaginal wall and vulva.

Tools and equipment:

1. Side lighting lamp.
2. Spoon-shaped vaginal mirrors.
3. Sterile gloves.
4. Glass slides.
5. Fixative solution (methyl alcohol, 95% ethyl alcohol; mixture of Nikiforov, May-Grunwald solution).
6. Air spatula.
7. Spirette (special aspiration device for ecto and endocervical aspirations).
8. Screen (a special device for taking endocervical swabs).
9. Cervex-Brush.
10. Volkmann's spoon.

Practical recommendations for cytological screening of cervical cancer:

Women with diagnosed pathology cervix. women with infection sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

Women with HPV infection in the ano-genital area.

- Women with HPV-positive test.

women with immunodeficiency condition (HIV/AIDS)

Women with contact and postcoital spotting.

Screening frequency:

- at the initial treatment - three annual tests in a row;
- for women aged 23-61 - after 3 years;
- for women 62 years old - after 5 years.

There is no reason to carry out screening for women aged 70 and over provided that adequate screening has been performed early and there are three documented consecutive satisfactory negative results.

Cytological test is not carried out:

- during menstruation;
- up to 12 weeks of the postpartum period;
- earlier than 48 hours after coitus;
- earlier than 48 hours after medical and diagnostic procedures on the neck uterus;
- in the presence of an inflammatory process of the pelvic organs.

There are three cytological classifications of cervical smears in the world: according to Papanicolaou, WHO (the morphological term “dysplasia” is used) and Bethesda System.

Papanicolaou classification (Pap smear, Pap test):

- “Normal smear type”. For 1st the class is characterized by a cytogram with a normal cellular composition;
 - “Inflammatory smear type”. Class 2 smears are characterized by the presence of epithelial cells with minor morphological changes (a slight increase in the nucleus), as well as the appearance of metaplastic epithelial cells;
 - "Doubtful type of smear." Grade 3 smears are distinguished by the appearance of cells with more pronounced morphological changes in the nuclei, designated as "dyskaryosis";
 - “Suspicious smear type”. Grade 4 smears - cells with atypia features and therefore suspicious of a malignant process are found; - “Obvious cancer”. Grade 5 smears are considered positive for cancer.
- WHO classification of cervical precancer
- N87 - cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), cervical dysplasia; N87.0 - cervical intraepithelial neoplasia I (CIN 1), mild cervical dysplasia; N87.1 - cervical intraepithelial neoplasia II (CIN 2), moderate cervical dysplasia; N87.2 - cervical intraepithelial neoplasia III (CIN 3), pronounced cervical dysplasia;
- N87.9 Cervical dysplasia; Unspecified. Histological research method Histological

research is objective and often final in the complex diagnosis of cervical pathology.

Refined morphological criteria for lesions of the cervix, a full-fledged histological conclusion are of decisive importance for determining the rational tactics of managing a sick woman and determining the prognosis of the disease.

Material for histological examination can be obtained using targeted biopsy, conization (ablation), scraping of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal, coneshaped amputation of the cervix, examination of the removed cervix.

The reliability of the histological method for diagnosing precancerous diseases and cervical cancer is 98.6%. The disadvantage of the method is the impossibility of multiple use in the examination of the same patient.

It is believed that cervical cancer can be caused by a sexually transmitted infection and the human papillomavirus (HPV).

Molecular biological methods of diagnostics They are aimed at detecting the smallest particles of DNA of the papillo virus we human and other microorganisms in the material (from the cervical canal and from the surface of the abnormal epithelium and exophytic warts). More than 120 types of HPV are known: 35 of them are found in the human anogenital tract. According to the potential of oncogenicity, HPV subgroups are distinguished:

- high oncogenic risk: types 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 48, 51, 56, 58, 59, 66, 68, 73 and 82;
- low oncogenic risk: types 6,11, 42, 43, 44.46, 47.50.

HPV detection methods are based on the ability of DNA to hybridize.

Heat-denatured viral DNA becomes single-stranded. Molecular biological methods can be divided into 3 groups:

- Non-amplifying (fix the presence of DNA or RNA directly in the preparation or on the filter).
- Amplification (fix the presence of DNA polymerase and DNA ligase,

a large number of identical DNA fragments are obtained and identified by electrophoresis, very sensitive methods).

Accurate DNA characterization can be done using real-time PCR. In addition, PCR allows you to determine the types of virus in the test sample.

The HPV-Digene test (Hybrid Capture II) is widely used to detect HPV. The method is well researched, standardized and has undoubted advantages both for practice and for improving the quality of clinical trials. The implementation of cervical cancer prevention and control programs contributes to the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals by providing universal access to sexual and reproductive health services to improve women's health. Prevention of cervical cancer Primary prevention:

- vaccination against HPV;
- carrying out sanitary and educational work of social and medical workers with the formation of a setting for a healthy lifestyle among women;
- timely treatment of STIs;
- use of barrier methods
contraception.

Secondary prevention:

- cytological screening;
- early diagnosis and treatment of persons with precancerous diseases of the cervix.

Tertiary prevention:

- complex treatment of cervical cancer
uterus, prevention of its recurrence.

The problem of background and precancerous diseases of the cervix is of great medical, biological and socio-economic importance - the treatment of patients with precancerous processes requires significantly less material costs than the treatment of cancer patients. Early diagnosis provides full rehabilitation of

patients and improves the quality and duration of their lives.

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